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**YÜKSEKÖĞRETİMDE NEO-LİBERALİZMİN GETİRDİĞİ YAPISAL
DÖNÜŞÜM VE EĞİTİMİN YATIRIMA DÖNÜŞMESİ: GİRİŞİMCİ
ÜNİVERSİTE MODELİ**

**THE STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION OF NEO-LIBERALISM IN HIGHER
EDUCATION AND THE TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATION INTO
INVESTMENT: THE ENTREPRENEURIAL UNIVERSITY MODEL**

Murat Cem Acaralp¹

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Özet

Neoliberalizm ile eğitimin değişime uğraması, ticari bir sektöre dönüşmesiyle eğitimdeki eşitsizlik baş göstermiş, bireyi aldığı eğitimin seviyesi, kalitesi ve içeriğiyle pazarda bir rekabete sokmuştur. Bu rekabetten güçlü çıkmak, kazanan olmak için, birey imkanlarını eğitime yönlendirerek kendini daha fazla geliştirmek, bilgi düzeyini arttırmak yolunu seçmek durumunda bırakılmıştır. Bu durum eğitim bir yatırım olması, insanında sermayeye dönüşmesine neden olmuştur. Bu çalışmada, belge tarama yöntemiyle derleme metodolojisi kullanılarak, girişimci üniversite modelinin tarihsel süreci, üniversitelerin neoliberalizm etkisiyle geçirdiği yapısal dönüşüm, bu dönüşümden kaçınmanın imkansızlığı ve girişimci üniversiteyi geliştiren temel etkenleri ve nedenleri araştıran bir değerlendirme yapılmıştır. Türkiye’de üniversitelerin, hükümetin benimsediği eğitim politikaları çerçevesinde girişimci üniversite modeline dönüşüm ve uyum sürecini hızlı uygulayacakları ve adaptasyon göstermek zorunda olacakları görülmüştür. Modelin olumsuz yanları ile birlikte olumlu yanlarına da belirtilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Neoliberalizm, Postmodernizm, Yapısal Dönüşüm, Eğitim Yatırımı, Girişimci Üniversite

¹ Yakın Doğu Üniversitesi, İletişim Fakültesi, Lefkoşe, KKTC, muratcem.acaralp@neu.edu.tr

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Abstract

With the transformation of education with neoliberalism and its transformation into a commercial sector, the inequality in education has emerged, putting the individual into a competition in the market with the level, quality and content of the education he received. In order to come out stronger from this competition, to become a winner, individuals have to choose the path to improve themselves and increase their knowledge level by directing their opportunities to their education. This situation has led to the fact that education is an investment and it has turned into a capital for people. In this study, using the document scanning method and compilation methodology, an evaluation has been made that investigates the historical process of the entrepreneurial university model, the structural transformation of universities under the influence of neoliberalism, the impossibility of avoiding this transformation, and the main factors and reasons that develop the entrepreneurial university. It has been observed that universities in Turkey will quickly implement the transformation and adaptation process to the entrepreneurial university model within the framework of the education policies adopted by the government, and they will have to adapt. Along with the negative aspects of the model, the positive aspects are also noted.

Keywords: Neoliberalism, Postmodernism, Structural Transformation, Educational Investment, Entrepreneurial University

1. Introduction

Problems and economic tensions arising from utilitarian approaches have led universities to pursue economic benefits other than finding and seeking the truth and have led to significant structural and institutional changes in higher education. For this reason, higher education institutions have been restructured according to their duties and jobs (Dias, September 1998). In fact, student events in various countries in 1968 had a great effect on the change in understanding of higher education. Problems such as the inability of students studying in higher education institutions to be employed in their fields, increasing unemployment and economic crises in 1970's accelerated the restructuring of higher education (Güven, 2002). West started this trend has spread to Turkey after 1980, together with liberalization and universities have to redefine themselves according to the new conditions. After YÖK, commercialization tendencies and large holding universities emerged. Governments and the industrial sector jointly supported such formations (Güven, 2002). With globalization, which is the new name of neoliberal economic policy, it has been concretized as states seek new partners in education expenditures in the first place in higher education. Increasing capitalist competition and dizzying developments in technology have put pressure on students to burden the financial burden on the one hand, with a new student profile on the other. Universities had to integrate with the capital (Timur, 2000).

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Neoliberalism

Neoliberalism is above all a theory of political-economic practices. This theory argues that the best way to boost human well-being is to release individual enterprise skills and freedoms within an institutional framework based on strong private property rights, free markets and free trade. (Harvey, 2015). Actually, it is not easy to define neoliberalism with a single expression. According to some, a new political economy; For some it is a new governance, for some it is a multiple strategy. (Aka, 2018).

According to Gamble, neoliberalism is a set of ideas and practices that overcome the blockage in the accumulation of capital, eliminate obstacles such as the welfare state one by one, and impose itself on the world through both international institutions and national states (Gamble, 2006). Gamble also argues that one cannot speak of a single neoliberalism (Davis Jr., 2009)

According to Harvey's claim, capitalism can turn the crises it causes in favor, and not rearrange the distribution of capital through "creative destruction" (Gambetti, 2009).

2.2. Neoliberalism in Education

The concepts of education reform, information technologies, e-learning, distance education, lifelong learning, and information society, which we often hear today, are the result of "Neoliberal" economic policies that have been carried out for nearly 25 years (Sayılan, 2006, p. 44). After the end of the Second World War, the economy developed during the war and scientific production based on projects started to be used. Its complete transformation took place with the neoliberal transformations after 1980. With the implementation of neoliberal

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economic policies that form the basis of globalization, education transformations that will meet the requirements of the new era have been experienced (Celik, 2016)

In the early 1980s, the first step was taken with the reforms made to re-determine the content and purpose of education according to market conditions, and as the second step, studies on the financing structure of education and training were put into practice. The third reform step is those aimed at reorganizing the role of education in social mobility and its egalitarian political function (Sayılan, 2006).

It has been inevitable that the neoliberal transformation, which extends to all sectors, will structure the education sector, which points to a wide market and great gain. The most important factor is to create the means of independence from the state. The reasons put forward to eliminate the objection of the public in this transformation were the poor quality in public schools, the neglect and inadequacy of educational buildings, the unwillingness of teachers in educational activities and the resulting weakness in education. In this transformation, an approach has been adopted in the form of no allowance other than providing teachers' staff to schools and forcing the school to be structured in a way to meet its own needs. However, the length of their working hours and summer holidays was discussed, and the excess salary they received in return was brought up for discussion (Kirisci, 2013).

With this effort, the discredit work is actually to guide private schools, private teaching institutions and private universities at the upper level. In fact, the private sector in education receives various support from the state and is rapidly developing and growing. Although it has positive results in some respects, it creates different effects in different parts of the society. Especially the foundation universities, which have increased in recent years, have come to the point that they cannot produce services and education unless they have a monetary equivalent by working with the logic of a business.

In this case, while the education sector started to earn money for those who manage the economy, it started to raise the kind of people the market wanted. With the effect of the public reforms, teachers started to be employed on a contractual basis and only half of the wages paid by the state to its permanent teachers were employed. Inadequate conditions and the education sector, which is getting worse with each passing day, naturally became inefficient and turned into an unequal commercial market where students receive education according to the financial opportunities they create individually.

As an extension of these planned studies, state universities were defined as entrepreneurial universities, contributing to the economy, earning profits, and closing the "consuming" departments that would not contribute to the neoliberal economy. In fact, "entrepreneurial university" does not have a fully explanatory definition as a concept. However, there are a number of approaches to distinguish the entrepreneurial university from other university models (Sakınc & Bursalıoğlu, 2012)

In the most general sense, the entrepreneurial university is expressed as a university that produces knowledge for economic and social use (Etzkowitz, 2003).

2.3. Education and Investment Relationship

The concept of investment can be expressed as the economic value that new additions to human capital (power) will bring to him at the end of the period. The capital here is man himself. All the gains he has received from the life he has taken up to that point are his acquisitions and accumulations. With the commercialization of education, the level of knowledge that every person has to get at the same level and equal has disappeared, and it has come to a point where people have to add to themselves from different sources of information and have to develop by paying a price.

In accordance with the free market economy, in order for an individual to be victorious from the competition in all areas of life, he must first differentiate by investing in himself, move himself to a different level from his competitors in the market and get ahead. In addition, of course, not only the investment in education will provide this, it has to allow the strengthening of his knowledge by applying the training he received. We can think of this as a business investment as companies do.

In order to achieve the life that the individual aims to live after education, first of all, he has to ensure that his education, which has become paid at every stage, is differentiated according to other individuals. A better job, a better salary, a better house, a better car, etc. The condition for having what they want will be through the investment expenditures it makes for itself in the capitalist system. At this point, education has turned from being a mere knowledge and profession to an effort to increase commercial capital, the subject of which is investment. When we evaluate it from this point of view, education becomes completely an investment, and all the expenditures made for it (which includes time, money and labor) become the capital of the individual. And when people step into life, they will realize that the biggest capital is actually the investments I have made in themselves.

Although the name used in business life is "human resources", when we start from this expression, we see that it is actually "human capital". The individual will continue to invest in himself in order to protect his capital throughout his life and not to lose the value of the capital. It would not be wrong to say that making capital valuable, increasing its value. It will endeavor to obtain maximum efficiency in order to continue its investments and raise the living standards. The maximum efficiency it will get will cause an increase in working life and accordingly increase in earnings. Even the fact that we can reach better economic conditions in the future by investing for themselves through education and training activities reveals that capital is human capital, that is human capital. The "education economy", which is a field of economic science, examines the concept of human (human) capital in detail.

2.4. Structural Transformation and Entrepreneurship in Universities

2.4.1. Entrepreneurial University

Universities today; It is trying to adapt to the global-information age under the pressure of a multivariate, complex and intense change and transformation. As a result of the pressures created by rapidly changing conditions, the strategic planning of universities and the change of strategic transformation, which is the cornerstone of it, is also necessary (Odabasi, 2006) It is known that the developed west conceptualized the name of this search as "Entrepreneurial

University" in many parts, changed its direction to reach this concept and made important changes and transformations to fulfill its requirements. In the political and economic order transformed by neoliberalism, structural changes and renewal of our universities are an inevitable result. This transformation will be positive for our universities to be among western universities in the international arena and to continue their existence. In fact, while performing this structural transformation, the necessity to find a suitable model for its own culture and social structure seems inevitable for success (Odabası, 2006)

It is necessary to make a complete definition in order to clarify the meaning of the concept of Entrepreneurial University and make the concept understandable. Although the concept of entrepreneurship is very old, its scientific investigation and definition took place at the beginning of this century. The views of the Austrian economist Joseph Schumpeter on entrepreneurship are accepted as part of a new economic model and the essence of this is "innovation". According to Schumpeter, this innovation expresses the combination of available resources and the entrepreneur can only be an entrepreneur if he is engaged in innovation activity (Tüsiad, 2002) .

Innovation, creativity and creating change are one of the basic features required to be an entrepreneur. Apart from this, taking risks, being a pioneer and having competitive thinking skills are also the basic components of entrepreneurial thinking (Basar, Tosunoglu, & Demirci, 2001). There is no doubt that the concept of entrepreneurship is a reflection of the age of globalization and the great change that the information society has shaped by neoliberalism.

The entrepreneurial university has been tried to be implemented rapidly by taking an example in universities in European countries, especially in its homeland America. Overall, the focus has shifted from the creation of independent organizations working between the university and industry to adding new features and functionality to the university (Lazzeroni & Piccaluga, 2003). As the rapidly changing micro and macro environments lead universities to think strategically and concentrate their functions, they are pushing them towards becoming an entrepreneurial university. Universities are becoming the main element of the industrial creativity system, both as providers of human capital in a knowledge-based society and by sowing the seeds for the establishment of new companies (Etzkowitz, Webster, Gebhardt, & Terra, 2000).

From this point of view, it can be argued that the entrepreneur university has three meanings:

- a. The university itself becomes an entrepreneur as an institution,
- b. Members of the university (academic staff, students, employees) turn themselves into entrepreneurs,
- c. The interaction between the university and the environment (the dual association between the university and the region) creates entrepreneurial structures.

All three structures constitute the mandatory conditions for being an entrepreneurial university. The existence of all three substances depends on the realization of the substance that precedes it. By fulfilling the requirements of the entrepreneurial university, it is possible to transform into a structure that adapts to the competition rules by paying attention to the

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issues of cost, effectiveness and efficiency, applies strong and innovations in information dissemination, directly contributes to those who take all these actions, and is prone to complete this structuring. (Odabası, 2006).

Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Index Indicator Set

Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Index consists of 5 (five) dimensions. There are 23 indicators under 5 dimensions².

Figure 1: Dimensions of Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Index

Source: Tübitak

Dimension 1: Scientific and Technological Research Activity³ (Weight Ratio: 20%)

- a. Number of scientific publications
- b. Number of citations
- c. Number of projects received from R&D and innovation support programs

² Within the scope of 23 indicators, data were provided by TÜBİTAK, YÖK, Universities, Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology, TPI, Ministry of Development, KOSGEB, TTGV, TÜBA and Universities.

³ Ministries / Institutions providing data for the first dimension: TÜBİTAK, Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology, Ministry of Development, YÖK, TTGV, TÜBA

Acaralp, M.C. (2021). *The Structural Transformation of Neo-Liberalism in Higher Education and The Transformation of Education into Investment: The Entrepreneurial University Model*. *GSI Journals Serie B: Advancements in Business and Economics*, 3 (2): 32-45.

- d. Fund amount received from R&D and innovation support programs
- e. Number of national and international science awards
- f. Number of graduates with a doctorate

Dimension 2: Intellectual Property Pool⁴ (Weight Ratio: 15%)

- a. Number of patent applications
- b. Number of patent documents
- c. Number of utility models / industrial design documents
- d. Number of international patent applications

Dimension 3: Collaboration and Interaction⁵ (Weight Ratio: 25%)

- a. Number of R&D and innovation projects conducted in university-industry cooperation
- b. Amount of funds received from R&D and innovation projects conducted in cooperation with university-industry
- c. Number of R&D and innovation projects carried out in international cooperation
- d. Fund amount obtained from international R&D and innovation collaborations
- e. Number of teaching staff / students in circulation

Dimension 4: Entrepreneurship and Innovation Culture⁶ (Weight Ratio: 15%)

- a. Number of courses on entrepreneurship and technology management at undergraduate and graduate levels
- b. Full time number of people working under the management of technology transfer office, techno park, incubation centers and TEKMER
- c. Existence of technology transfer office structuring
- d. Number of entrepreneurships, technology management and innovation management training / certificate programs organized outside the university

Dimension 5: Economic Contribution and Commercialization⁷ (Weight Ratio: 25%)

⁴ Ministries / Institutions providing data for the second dimension: TPI, YÖK, Universities

⁵ Ministries / Institutions providing data to the third dimension: TÜBİTAK, YÖK, Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology, Ministry of Development, TTTGV, Universities

⁶ Ministries / Institutions providing data to the fourth dimension: Universities, Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology, KOSGEB, TÜBİTAK

⁷ Ministries / Institutions providing data for the fifth dimension: Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology, KOSGEB, Universities, TUBITAK, YOK, TPE

Acaralp, M.C. (2021). *The Structural Transformation of Neo-Liberalism in Higher Education and The Transformation of Education into Investment: The Entrepreneurial University Model*. *GSI Journals Serie B: Advancements in Business and Economics*, 3 (2): 32-45.

- a. Number of active companies that academicians have partners or owned in technoparks, incubation centers, TEKMERs
- b. Number of active companies that university students or those who have graduated in the last five years, in technoparks, incubation centers, TEKMER's partners or owned
- c. The number of people employed by academicians in technoparks, incubation centers, TEKMER's partners or companies owned by them
- d. Number of patents / utility models / industrial designs licensed

2.4.2. The Phases of Change in Universities

Wissema (2009) explains the change in universities by classifying them as science-focused medieval university (First Generation), education and research-oriented Humboldt-type university (Second Generation), and entrepreneurial and socially integrated (Third Generation) university that expresses the new form of universities today (Wissema, 2009)

2.4.2.1. Middle Ages University (First Generation)

The medieval age covers a period of about a thousand years, coming after the Greek - Roman culture and reaching the Age of Enlightenment. The medieval age is considered a transitional period between Antiquity and the Renaissance. Although these schools are few in number, they did not fully develop until the 13th century[®] and could not go beyond having a regional character. Before the 13th century, there were no educational and training institutions similar to universities in today's sense for a long time. Before medieval universities, there were churches, cathedrals and monasteries in Europe, and centers where private tutors gave lectures to a certain group. These centers were called "studium generale" (Rukançı & Anameriç, 2010). While cathedrals and monasteries were the institutions where education and training were carried out in the medieval Scholastic Period and until the 12th century, these schools lost their influence in the 12th century and lost their superiority to the universities. Universities were not established all at once in the Middle Ages. These came about step by step. In the Middle Ages, "universitas", which means excellence was used for a series of collaborative associations. Therefore, this concept is used to denote the association of teachers and students. (Wissema, 2009) (Ozkul, 2006).

2.4.2.2. Humboldt Type University (Second Generation)

While the influence of the church on universities has decreased since the Renaissance, the influence of the state has started to increase in the world. In these periods, with the decrease of the influence of the church, the state or political authority started to be effective in the selection of professors and students at the university and to increase its control over universities. Meanwhile, the question of what will be taught at the university also came to the agenda[®] and the discussions mostly focused on teaching programs. Thus, the modern university (Second Generation University), which centered the production of scientific

knowledge and the principle of free and universal education, was born in Germany with the effect of the French Revolution and the Napoleonic Wars (Ciftçi, 2010) In France, these developments took place with the University Law enacted by Napoleon in 1806, with the establishment of elite higher education institutions instead of universities (Timur, 2000).

In the model, the university should have scientific and organizational autonomy and should only be subjected to financial control, it is managed by the boards and the rector, who is seen as the first among equals, is elected by the university professors for a year; developing "tenure" systems that give professors job security; it is envisaged that the university will be open to all segments of the society within the scope of equal opportunity and be financed by the state (Ciftçi, 2010).

2.4.2.3. Entrepreneurial University (Third Generation)

The process of transformation into an information society and transition to an information economy necessitated the change of higher education institutions responsible for the production and sharing of knowledge. Third generation universities; It has three important purposes as research, education and serving the society (Wissema, 2009).

In line with these purposes, universities tend to turn into mechanisms that directly generate added value by establishing cooperation and partnership with all segments of the society, as well as producing information in line with their education and research missions and making this information available to the society and industrial organizations (Yıldırım, 2014).

Third generation university model with the aim of adapting to the demands of the outside world and the demands of the market; It turns into a community of organizations that undertake the functions of education, research and providing services to the society (Ciftçi, 2010).

9 main features of third generation universities

1. Basic research continues to be the central activity of the university.
2. Studies are transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary.
3. Network universities. They cooperate with industry, R&D companies, investors and other universities.
4. They are active in markets where international competition prevails. They actively compete with each other to find the best academics and students and to make the best research contracts with the industry.
5. Although they usually do not avoid being a mass university, they create special opportunities for the best and brightest students and academics.
6. They adopt the concepts of interdisciplinary consensus and creativity as a driving force equivalent to rational scientific methods.
7. They are cosmopolitan. They adopt English as the language of instruction.
8. As universities are seen as the cradle of new entrepreneurial activities, the use of knowledge, in addition to the traditional research and educational goals, becomes the third goal of universities.

Acaralp, M.C. (2021). *The Structural Transformation of Neo-Liberalism in Higher Education and The Transformation of Education into Investment: The Entrepreneurial University Model*. *GSI Journals Serie B: Advancements in Business and Economics*, 3 (2): 32-45.

9. They will be less dependent on official legislation.

Entrepreneurial University Models

Five models emerge in the determination of the university's entrepreneurial culture in terms of organizational reform and entrepreneurial activities, based on the university tradition, mission, and economic, political and socio-cultural values (Yokoyama, 2006)

University model	Features
Sample Type University (Tokyo University)	Corporate awareness; Entrepreneurial culture; Governance, leadership and financial resources defined according to the basis, institutional strategic planning; The responsibility of giving increasing accounts
Entrepreneur-Oriented University (Waseda University)	Wide entrepreneurial activities; Market-oriented corporate policies; Conflict between academic and entrepreneurial values; the concept of business
Beginner Entrepreneur University (Nottingham University)	Constrained dependency to public resources, an entrepreneurial university ID; Contribution to Regional Economy
Compatible Entrepreneurial University (Surrey University)	Corporate future vision; Resources of foreign funds; Market-oriented management and business, entrepreneurial and academic culture
Ideal University Model	Autonomous and self-confident; Responsibility and risk sharing between entrepreneurial activities and actors; Integration between the entrepreneurial and academic culture and the managerial and peer culture

Table 1: Types of Entrepreneurial Universities Universities Take in Entrepreneurship Path (Yokoyama, 2006)

Source: (Sakinc & Bursalioglu, 2012)

3. Method

Qualitative research method was used, the information obtained from secondary data sources as a data collection tool was examined with compilation methodology by using document scanning method. "Is it inevitable that the entrepreneur university model, the product of the structural transformation brought about by neoliberalism, exists for higher education? What should be the correct point of view? " "For success in higher education; Is the entrepreneurial university a suitable model for Turkish social structure? " answers were sought.

4. Findings and Conclusion

According to AKA, positive identities (whites, rich, power and ambition enthusiasts, those who always have the drive to win, those who reproduce the existing mechanism, the masculine mentality and those who enjoy the pain of others, those who use the instrumental mind very well, etc.) admire neoliberalism and they do everything in their power to improve. Neoliberalism naturally prefers these identities and removes all the obstacles in its way one by one (Aka, 2018).

In the context of neoliberalism pointing to the new imperialist era, if we consider that it is both a big hump on the back of the state and a star sector that will create high financial

resources for the state, it will be inevitable to undergo a structural transformation. Since the first factor here is to independence from the state, the existence of situations that will prevent this transformation will not be preferred. First of all, the necessity of the process, which started with the propaganda that its inadequacy would be the biggest obstacle to development, has settled with the privatization of education, the weakening of public schools and the fact that private schools have become the reason of preference. The transformation in universities has been easier than compulsory education. Because without the need for discrediting and weakening, a transition to a painless transformation process is realized with the goal of having a job with guaranteed high income and position gain in a period where privatization is progressing rapidly at the end of wide research fields, higher quality, labels, opportunities and training process. Unless viewed from a broad perspective, although it is an instantly attractive and preferable situation, it is inevitable that the high income and position step will be blocked in the following years. The speed in the structural transformation of education is a process that progresses much faster than the development of industry and medium-sized enterprises. In fact, this is exactly what Neoliberalism wants. The gap between the number of individuals in the educational process and the number of trained people needed by the industry is not something that Neoliberalism cares about. This is a racing and competitive environment. According to the discourse of neoliberalism, "If you are in the same status, you should try harder, read more and get rid of your competitors", the equivalent of "spend more money on your education, get a higher-level education, human capital is a human capital, and capital must be constantly increased in order not to be crushed under other capitals. "That high income and position you want will be yours."

This is not just a person trying to exist in competition by investing in himself. Every player of this transformation must know that he cannot escape this competition on his own platform at every stage, at all stages. The new order constructed by neoliberalism for the life of the individual is in a similar situation within educational institutions and industrial establishments. The entrepreneurial college jacket has been the perfect name for this occasion. It should also be said that it has more positive sides than it has negative sides. The high level of performance and practice of universities in order to become an entrepreneurial university means that universities are seen as an investment that they make to increase the capital value of themselves, which is actually capital, by investing in themselves, just as the individual is self-capital and investing in himself. Every living organism has to increase its influence area as it grows. The efforts of universities to expand their sphere of influence can be seen as a positive situation. A more efficient, stronger, more successful, more comprehensive and larger university will be more preferred and will turn into a science industry that produces more effective and quality production.

We have to admit that education is now an industry and functions as a business in universities. The fact that there is a structural transformation happening throughout the world is certain that we are not obliged to deny or accept this process, which only who will adopt it first, who will be late but will have to accept it. It is necessary to keep up with the transformation in order to live in better conditions in the rapidly developing technology and rapidly industrializing society and to have a good position in the society. During a period in which academicians were transformed into technocrats, the necessity of conducting more research, producing more information, and the necessity of the knowledge produced

according to scientific rules became one of the main steps in the transformation of the entrepreneurial university. From a positive point of view, it makes it impossible to reach academic career stages without deserving. Hard-working scientists, equipped with quality information, will emerge, which will mean an increase in the number of well-equipped and knowledgeable faculty members. Better university professors mean better university education students. It is certain that the price spent on education will make a significant contribution to development and progress. In this case, it will become an indisputable element that every investment made by the individual will mean a more valuable capital.

5. Limitations and Recommendations

The evaluation made within the framework of the information collected through document scanning is the limitation of this study. It is recommended to conduct an empirical study to examine and evaluate the reflections and concrete results of the concept of entrepreneurial university on faculty, students and society. the universities of Turkey, proximity to the entrepreneurial university model, susceptibility and is working to be able to demonstrate the applicability of the university as a result is arguable. The fact that such a study will require a more detailed study of the concept of human (human) capital in "education economics", which is an area of economics, by clarifying the positive and negative aspects of the existence of the concept with numerical results will make an important contribution to the literature.

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